

Bionomia/OpenRefine/Wikidata

“Collection items at”

Workflow

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Introduction

Bionomia (<https://bionomia.net/>) is described in English Wikipedia as:

“a database and database entry tool which permits the name strings of collectors, and of taxonomists who determine specimen data, to be assigned to the unique person who collected or identified the specimen. If the person is living, this is done via their [ORCID ID](#), and if dead, via their [Wikidata](#) identifier. It thereby resolves ambiguity where two or more collectors have similar names; or where one collector has worked under two names, or a single name written in two or more ways. The specimen data associated with, and used by, Bionomia are the aggregated [GBIF](#) data.¹”

As a result of the attribution work undertaken within Bionomia, Frictionless data (<https://frictionlessdata.io/>) packages are produced by that website. The data held in those packages are able to be uploaded into OpenRefine (<https://openrefine.org/>). OpenRefine is a powerful tool used to clean, reconcile and prepare data for ingestion into collection management systems and is able to be used to directly edit and enrich Wikidata (<https://www.wikidata.org>).

This workflow uses both Bionomia frictionless data packages and OpenRefine to assist with the bulk editing and enrichment of natural history specimen collector Wikidata items. By adding a “collection items at” ([P11146](#)) statement to those items, Wikidata links natural history specimen collectors to the institution that holds their collections.

Motivation

This workflow ensures collections are semantically linked to the collectors that have contributed specimens to those collections. This helps improve the visibility of natural history collections. It also has the potential to help institutions that hold natural history collections to obtain data on the collectors who have contributed to those collections.

The types of data that can be accessed after this editing of Wikidata include third party institution identifiers relating to the collector such as ORCID, VIAF, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, and so on. The full name and alias', birth and death dates of the collector as well as affiliation and/or employment information and information on the research expeditions the collector participated in, may also be available via Wikidata.

As Wikidata is licensed for reuse under a Creative Commons zero (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.en>) licence, all this data can be reused or imported into an institution's Collection Management System. This assists with the roundtripping of data by the institution holding the relevant collection.

¹ [Bionomia Wikipedia article](#). 30 September 2025. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Upon completion, this workflow can also contribute to an institution's effort to collate a comprehensive collector list. Once "collection items at" statements have been added to appropriate collector Wikidata items that statement can then be queried to generate a list of collectors who have donated specimens to a particular collection.

Workflow

This document will use the example of the New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD) dataset published in GBIF by the Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research group of the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute.

<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a862>

GBIF

Bionomia uses data from datasets added by institutions to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). The first step in this workflow is to therefore find the GBIF collection dataset Bionomia uses in order to extract collector name strings for a particular collection held by an institution.

Go to the GBIF website (<https://www.gbif.org/>) and click the "Publishers" tab (<https://www.gbif.org/publisher/search?q=>) to search for the institution that publishes the data to GBIF. Using the example given in this workflow the term "Landcare Research" is searched and GBIF returns a profile page for that institution. See <https://www.gbif.org/publisher/6b2f029b-7823-4b84-9c30-31ff364238fe>

Click the "datasets" tab to obtain a list of the datasets (https://www.gbif.org/dataset/search?publishing_org=6b2f029b-7823-4b84-9c30-31ff364238fe) that have been published by that institution in GBIF. Select the appropriate dataset, in this case the the New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD) dataset (<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a862>) and copy the GBIF URL for that dataset. The important part of that URL is the dataset identifier listed after the <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/> portion of the URL, in this case "ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a862".

Bionomia

Then go to Bionomia and search for that dataset in Bionomia. The New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD) dataset from GBIF can be found in Bionomia either by searching for the dataset name or by using the GBIF dataset identifier (in this case ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a862) with "https://bionomia.net/dataset/" placed in front of it. i.e. <https://bionomia.net/dataset/ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a862>.

New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD)
<https://gbif.org/dataset/ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a8b2>

Specimen data from the New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD), Landcare Research, New Zealand.

Primary administrative contact
 Eric McKenzie
 mckenziee@landcareresearch.co.nz

Frictionless Data
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10592076
 collectors & determiners: 449 Code

Refresh

449 people claimed or were attributed specimens represented in this dataset Progress: 62%

Name	Birth - Death	Location	Collected	Identified
John Errol Chandos Aberdeen	1913 - 1996	United Kingdom; United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland	Collected Agaricaceae	and identified Agaricaceae
Nancy Adams	May 19, 1926 - March 27, 2007	New Zealand	Collected Rhodmelaceae	and identified Rhodmelaceae
Alfred Ade	July 17, 1876 - November 12, 1968	Germany	Collected Venturiaceae	and identified Rosaceae
John Leonard Alcorn	1937 - November 02, 2021	Australia	Collected Pleosporaceae	and identified Pleosporaceae
Harry Allan	April 27, 1882 - October 29, 1957	New Zealand	Collected Asteraceae	and identified Asteraceae
Harry Ardell Allard	January 28, 1880 - February 25, 1963	United States	Collected Cladoniaceae	and identified Cyperaceae
Betty Molesworth Allen	July 21, 1913 - October 11, 2002	New Zealand	Collected Polypodiaceae	and identified Asteraceae
Arthur Hugh Garfit Alston	September 04, 1902 - March 17, 1988	United Kingdom; United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland	Collected Polypodiaceae	and identified Selaginellaceae
Harry Warren Anderson	1885 - 1971		Collected Chaconiaceae	and identified Venturiaceae

Screenshot of Bionomia. 30 September 2025. Bionomia. Reused with permission.

As can be seen from the above screenshot, as at 30 September 2025, the PDD dataset is 62% complete. 449 people in this dataset have themselves claimed, or have had specimens attributed to them by Bionomia scribes.

More information on how to become a Bionomia scribe and to undertake this attribution work can be found at <https://doi.org/10.25334/AXVE-E198>.

In order to have this data uploaded in Wikidata, the data first needs to be downloaded from Bionomia.

Specimen data from the New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD), Landcare Research, New Zealand.

Primary administrative contact
 Eric McKenzie
 mckenziee@landcareresearch.co.nz

Frictionless Data
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10592076

Frictionless Data

- Descriptor (JSON)
- Users (csv, zip)
- Unascribed (csv, zip)
- Problem Determiner Dates (csv, zip)
- Problem Collector Dates (csv, zip)
- Occurrences (csv, zip)
- Attributions (csv, zip)
- Articles (csv, zip)
- Article Occurrences (csv, zip)

Created 2025-07-14 07:29:26 UTC

Refresh

Screenshot of Bionomia. 30 September 2025. Bionomia. Reused with permission.

This download of data can be achieved by going to the left hand side of the Bionomia profile for the PDD dataset and clicking the frictionless data tab. Select the “Attributions” data package and download this to your computer. This will download a zip file which will need to be clicked on in your downloads folder to obtain the CSV attributions file.

Once the CSV file has been opened and extracted from the zip file it can then be uploaded into OpenRefine.

OpenRefine

If you have OpenRefine installed on your computer, open OpenRefine. If you do not, go to this website link <https://openrefine.org/docs/manual/installing> and follow the instructions to install OpenRefine on your computer. Then open the tool.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Start the import of the Bionomia attributions CSV file by creating a project in OpenRefine. Select “Create project” then select “This computer” and press the “choose file” tab and select the Bionomia attributions CSV file from your downloads folder. Then press the “next” button.

	user_id	occurrence_id	identifiedBy	recordedBy	createdBy	createdByURI	createdDateTime	ms
1.	12725	1135716184	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-01-02T23:52:05Z	
2.	12725	1135716185	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-11-05T03:51:52Z	
3.	12466	1135716187	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3180318		Bionomia Bot		2020-01-12T17:07:24Z	
4.	97934	1135716188	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21502748	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21502748	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2023-04-23T09:47:31Z	
5.	13223	1135716191		http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6205005	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2019-11-30T08:31:56Z	
6.	12391	1135716192	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q4212529		Siobhan Leachman	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-7721	2021-04-29T03:13:12Z	
7.	13223	1135716192		http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6205005	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2019-11-29T21:05:50Z	
8.	2188	1135716195	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T19:59:31Z	
9.	2188	1135716196	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T20:10:12Z	
10.	2188	1135716198	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T20:10:12Z	
11.	45717	1135716198		https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9400-7112	Siobhan Leachman	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-7721	2022-07-12T23:45:17Z	
12.	89762	1135716199	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21337939	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21337939	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2022-01-19T04:57:16Z	
13.	89762	1135716201	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21337939	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21337939	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2022-01-19T04:57:16Z	
14.	2188	1135716203	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T20:10:12Z	
15.	43467	1135716203		http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q17418645	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-01-11T08:57:30Z	
16.	2188	1135716204	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T19:59:31Z	
17.	12725	1135716205	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137		Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-11-05T03:51:49Z	
18.	2188	1135716206	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T19:59:31Z	
19.	43467	1135716207	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q17418645	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q17418645	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-01-11T08:42:09Z	

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Create a project name and any tags you wish to organise the project in OpenRefine. Check how the data is displayed in OpenRefine. Once you are happy press “create project”.

OpenRefine New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD) csv

Facet / Filter Undo / Redo 0 / 0

83,428 rows

Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows

Extensions Wikibase

Using facets and filters

Use facets and filters to select subsets of your data to act on. Choose facet and filter methods from the menus at the top of each data column.

Not sure how to get started? Watch these screencasts

	user_id	occurrence_id	identifiedBy	recordedBy	createdBy	createdByURI	createdDateTime	modifiedDateTime
1.	12725	1135716184	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-01-02T23:52:05Z	
2.	12725	1135716185	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3435137	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2020-11-05T03:51:52Z	
3.	12466	1135716187	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3180318		Bionomia Bot		2020-01-12T17:07:24Z	
4.	97934	1135716188	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21502748	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21502748	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2023-04-23T09:47:31Z	
5.	13223	1135716191		http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6205005	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2019-11-30T08:31:56Z	
6.	12391	1135716192	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q4212529		Siobhan Leachman	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5396-7721	2021-04-29T03:13:12Z	
7.	13223	1135716192		http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6205005	Bevan Weir	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2580-0701	2019-11-29T21:05:56Z	
8.	2188	1135716196	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T19:59:31Z	
9.	2188	1135716196	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T20:10:12Z	
10.	2188	1135716198	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0761-9116	Jerry Cooper	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4994-3897	2019-11-05T20:10:12Z	

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

It is possible to work on the needed data within this OpenRefine project. However these Bionomia datasets are frequently very large as they contain all the species occurrence data for the collection. It is therefore often easier to create a separate, new OpenRefine project in order to work on just the “recordedBy” data.

The “recordedBy” column of this dataset contains either URL link to the ORCID identifier, if the collector is living, or the URL link to the Wikidata item, if the collector is deceased, for each specimen in that dataset that has been attributed to a particular collector in Bionomia.

recordedBy

createdBy

Facet

Text filter

Edit cells

Edit column

Transpose

Sort...

View

Reconcile

Text facet

Numeric facet

Timeline facet

Scatterplot facet...

Custom text facet...

Custom numeric facet...

Customized facets

ustwick

Bevan Weir

Deter Kenneth Charles Austwick

Bevan Weir

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

In order to create a smaller, more manageable OpenRefine project, go to the “recordedBy” column in OpenRefine. At the “recordedBy” column press the dropdown menu and “Facet” the column by “Text facet”.

recordedBy change

316 choices Sort by: name count Cluster

- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100156193> 4
- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100740492> 21
- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1028738> 1
- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q10289602> 1
- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105310988> 1
- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105749753> 3
- <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105758334> 103

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will produce a “recordedBy” box in the facet/filter tab on the left hand side of the project. In this box the group of recordedBy identifiers are all clustered by identifier rather than by each species occurrence. Press the “choices” link at the top left of the “recordedBy” box next to the number of choices.

Facet choices as Tab Separated Values

```

http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100156193      4
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100740492     21
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1028738      1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q10289602     1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105310988     1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105749753     3
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105758334    103
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106457720     3
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106477140     2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106483418     1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1064899       2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106888973     2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q107858        1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q108911267     1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q110178035     2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q113299        1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q113642398     2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114185513     3
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114223107     1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114245826     5
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114249993     2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114352527     5
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114529060     2
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116985644     1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q11925777      1
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q119459816     3

```

Close

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

A pop up box will appear giving the faceted choices as Tab Separated Values.

Copy this text and then add it to either a Google Sheets document or an Excel spreadsheet. In the below example a screenshot shows the copied faceted choices that have been pasted into a Google Sheets document. Add a row at the top of the sheet to insert column names and then download the Google sheet as an excel spreadsheet. Alternatively in an Excel spreadsheet insert a column at the top of the sheet in order to add column names and then save the Excel spreadsheet in preparation for the next step.

D8 ▾ | *fx*

	A	B	C
1	Wikidata/ORCID	Counts	
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100156193	4	
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100740492	21	
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1028738	1	
5	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q10289602	1	
6	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105310988	1	
7	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105749753	3	
8	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105758334	103	
9	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106457720	3	
10	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106477140	2	
11	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106483418	1	
12	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106483418	2	
13	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106483418	2	

Screenshot of Google spreadsheet. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Use the created Excel spreadsheet to start a new OpenRefine project following the steps outlined at the beginning of this workflow.

 OpenRefine New Zealand Fungal and Plant Disease Collection (PDD) Sheet1 csv [Permalink](#)

Facet / Filter Undo / Redo 0 / 0 <

428 rows

Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows

Using facets and filters

Use facets and filters to select subsets of your data to act on. Choose facet and filter methods from the menus at the top of each data column.

Not sure how to get started?
[Watch these screencasts](#)

	All	Wikidata/ORCID	Counts
★	1.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100156193	4
★	2.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100740492	21
★	3.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1028738	1
★	4.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q10289602	1
★	5.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105310988	1
★	6.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105749753	3
★	7.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q105758334	103
★	8.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106457720	3
★	9.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106477140	2
★	10.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q106483418	1

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

As the Wikidata and ORCID column contains URLs to both the Wikidata items and ORCID profiles it is recommended to separate these two into different columns.

To do this, first split the Wikidata/ORCID column by selecting that column dropdown, selecting “Edit column” and then select “Split into several columns...”.

428 rows

Show as: **rows** records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows

All	Wikidata/ORCID	Counts
1.	Facet	entity/Q100156193 4
2.	Text filter	entity/Q100740492 21
3.		entity/Q1028738 1
4.	Edit cells	entity/Q10289602 1
5.	Edit column	
6.	Transpose	
7.	Sort...	
8.	View	
9.	Reconcile	
11.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100156193	
12.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100740492	
13.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1028738	
14.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q10289602	
15.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100156193	
16.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100740492	
17.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1028738	
18.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q10289602	
19.	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q114223107	1

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Split on the separator <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/> by adding this text to the Separator box as shown below.

Split column "Wikidata/ORCID" into several columns

How to split column

by separator

Separator regular expression

Split into columns at most (leave blank for no limit)

by field lengths

List of integers separated by commas, e.g. 5, 7, 15

After splitting

Guess cell type

Remove this column

OK

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will create a new column made up of Wikidata QIDs.

428 rows				
Show as: rows records		Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows		
All	Wikidata/ORCID 1	Wikidata/ORCID 2	Counts	
☆	1.	Q100156193	4	
☆	2.	Q100740492	21	
☆	3.	Q1028738	1	
☆	4.	Q10289602	1	
☆	5.	Q105310988	1	
☆	6.	Q105749753	3	
☆	7.	Q105758334	103	
☆	8.	Q106457720	3	
☆	9.	Q106477140	2	edit
☆	10.	Q106483418	1	
☆	11.	Q1064899	2	
☆	12.	Q106888973	2	
☆	13.	Q107858	1	
☆	14.	Q108911267	1	
☆	15.	Q110178035	2	
☆	16.	Q113299	1	
☆	17.	Q113642398	2	
☆	18.	Q114185513	3	
☆	19.	Q114223107	1	

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Repeat the above process, that is again split the original Wikidata/ORCID column, but this time based on the separator "<https://orcid.org/>". This will result in the addition of another column to the OpenRefine project but this time it will be made up of ORCID identifiers.

428 rows				
Show as: rows records		Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows		
All	Wikidata/ORCID 1 1	Wikidata/ORCID 1 2	Wikidata/ORCID 2	Counts
☆	327.		Q93319279	291
☆	328.		Q95970921	1
☆	329.		Q96781837	12
☆	330.		Q96781882	5
☆	331.		Q97744895	3
☆	332.		Q98023097	1
☆	333.		Q99399217	1
☆	334.		Q99526413	1
☆	335.		Q99678117	1
☆	336.	0000-0001-5229-1709		65
☆	337.	0000-0001-5309-6438		717
☆	338.	0000-0001-5342-9909		1
☆	339.	0000-0001-5970-8343		3
☆	340.	0000-0001-6699-7083		328

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

At this point it is now time to reconcile both columns - the Wikidata Qid column and the ORCID column - against Wikidata. Go to the Wikidata QID column, click the drop down, go to "Reconcile" and pick "Start reconciling...".

RCid 1 2	Wikidata/ORCID 2	Counts
	Facet	4
	Text filter	21
	Edit cells	1
	Edit column	1
	Transpose	3
	Sort...	103
	View	3
	Reconcile	2
	Q1064899	
	Q106888973	
	Q107858	
	Q108911267	
	Q110178035	
	Q113299	
	Q113642398	

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

OpenRefine will then ask you to pick the reconciliation service. OpenRefine offers Wikidata as a default service and it is possible to add other reconciliation services to OpenRefine. Select the Wikidata reconciliation service.

Reconcile column Wikidata/ORCID 2

Select a service to reconcile against:

<input type="radio"/>	Wikimedia Commons (en) https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Wikidata reconci.link (en) https://wikidata.reconci.link/en/api	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/>	ORCID https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/>	Bionomia https://api.bionomia.net/reconcile	<input type="button" value="✕"/>

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

OpenRefine will then suggest the type of entity against which the data in the dataset should be reconciled. As we are dealing with human scientific collectors, the appropriate type of entity to choose is “human”.

Reconcile column Wikidata/ORCID 2

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

human
 Q5
 entity
 Q35120

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
Wikidata/ORCID 1 1	<input type="text"/>
Wikidata/ORCID 1 2	<input type="text"/>
Counts	<input type="text"/>

Reconcile against type:

Reconcile against no particular type

Auto-match candidates with high confidence

Maximum number of candidates to return

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then press “start reconciling...”. As OpenRefine is reconciling Wikidata QIDs against Wikidata the reconciliation should take place relatively quickly and should also be 100% complete.

Repeat this process for the ORCID column. That is, go to the ORCID column, select the dropdown menu, choose “Reconcil” and select “start reconciling...”. Again pick the Wikidata reconciliation service and choose to reconcile against human as the type of entity.

Once OpenRefine has completed this reconciliation for the ORCID identifier column is likely to look like the screenshot below.

Wikidata/ORCID 1 2	Wikidata/ORCID 2	Counts
0000-0001-5309-6438 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Peter Kenneth Buchanan (13) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match		717
0000-0001-5342-9909 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brian Patrick Looney (12) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match		1
0000-0001-5970-8343 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mats Thulin (11) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match		3

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

In order for the reconciliation to be complete the OpenRefine user will have to manually match the ORCID to the Wikidata item suggested by clicking the single checkmark.

Wikidata/ORCID 1 2	Wikidata/ORCID 2	Counts
Peter Kenneth Buchanan Choose new match		717
Brian Patrick Looney Choose new match		1
0000-0001-5970-8343 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mats Thulin (11) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Match this cell <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Match all identical cells <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cancel	3
0000-0001-6699-7083 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Peter de Lange (19) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	 Mats Thulin (Q6006366) Swedish botanist (born 1948)	
0000-0001-6894-2158 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Alastair W. Robertson (12)		

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

By far the majority of the suggestions by OpenRefine are a match, however there may be occasions where OpenRefine suggests several humans to match the ORCID against.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Where this happens it is advisable to go to <https://orcid.org/> and search on the orcid number to confirm the name attached to the ORCID.

Screenshot of ORCID profile.

Then select that match in OpenRefine.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once reconciliation has finished then create a Wikibase schema in preparation for uploading data to Wikidata. Press the Wikibase tab on the right hand side of OpenRefine, and select “Edit Wikibase schema” from the dropdown.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will open a schema tab, along with an Issues and Preview tab for your project.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Press the “Add item” to start creating your schema.

428 rows Schema * Issues 1 Preview

Target Wikibase instance: Wikidata

Start from an existing schema: Select... Save schema

Wikidata/ORCID 1 1 Wikidata/ORCID 1 2 Wikidata/ORCID 2 Counts

type item or drag reconciled column remove

Terms
no labels, descriptions or aliases added + add term

Statements
no statements added + add statement

Add item Save schema changes Discard changes

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Drag one of the reconciled columns to the “type item or drag reconciled column” box and press “add statement” to start creating the statements you want to add to the Wikidata item for the collector.

Wikidata/ORCID 1 2 remove

Terms
no labels, descriptions or aliases added + add term

Statements

collection items at New Zealand Fungarium remove configure + add qualifier

▶ 1 references

copy remove

stated in Bionomia remove

reference URL https://bionomia.ne remove

retrieved 2025-10-25 remove

+ add
+ add reference
+ add value

occupation botanical collector remove configure + add qualifier

▶ 1 references

copy remove

stated in Bionomia remove

+ add
+ add reference
+ add value
+ add statement

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then add the property “collection items at” ([P11146](#)) and the Wikidata item for the name of the collection the specimens are held at. In this example the collection is the New Zealand Fungarium <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q65963052>.

A reference should also be added to support this statement. In this case as the data was obtained from Bionomia, a “stated in” ([P248](#)) statement has been added referencing Bionomia ([Q64446405](#)). The Bionomia dataset URL and a retrieved date should also be added to this reference.

It is also possible to add other statements to the collector Wikidata item. For example in this case the collector has the “occupation” ([P106](#)) of “botanical collector” ([Q2083925](#)). Wikidata has a very wide definition of the property “occupation” and “botanical collector” in this context also includes collectors of fungi. Again ensure any statements made are supported with a reference. In this case again a “stated in” statement can be added referencing Bionomia.

Once the schema is complete, check for issues by clicking the issues tab. As this schema is adding a statement using the Wikidata “Occupation” property, OpenRefine will automatically issue a warning saying the Wikidata item this statement is being added to should have an “instance of” statement. This issue can be ignored as data is being added to existing Wikidata items that can be assumed to already have an “instance of” statement.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The preview tab should also be checked to ensure all the editing statements will be generated as expected.

428 rows Schema * Issues 2 Preview Extensions Wikibase ▾

This tab shows the first edits (out of 2) that will be made once you upload the changes to Wikidata. You can use facets to inspect the edits on particular items.

Peter Kenneth Buchanan (Q21506603)

occupation (P106)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> botanical collector (Q2083925) ▼ 1 references stated in (P248) Bionomia (Q64446405)
collection items at (P11146)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Zealand Fungarium (Q65963052) ▼ 1 references reference URL (P854) https://bionomia.net/dataset/ee27b1b0-3b55-11dc-8c18-b8a03c50a862 stated in (P248) Bionomia (Q64446405) retrieved (P813) 25 October 2025

Brian Patrick Looney (Q36517165)

occupation (P106)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> botanical collector (Q2083925) ▶ 1 references
collection items at (P11146)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Zealand Fungarium (Q65963052) ▶ 1 references

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once satisfied that issues have been checked and resolved and a preview of the data has been undertaken, the data can then be uploaded into Wikidata. Go to the Wikibase tab on the top right of OpenRefine, and select “Upload edits to Wikibase” from the dropdown menu.

Extensions Wikibase ▾

- Manage Wikibase instances...
- Edit Wikibase schema
- Manage schemas...
- Manage Wikibase account...
- Upload edits to Wikibase...
- Export to QuickStatements

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will take you to a pop up window requesting you log into your Wikidata account.

Wikidata account

Logging in to [Wikidata](#) lets you upload edits directly from OpenRefine.

You are encouraged to login with [bot passwords](#), see this [wiki page](#) to learn how to get one.

Username

Password

Remember me [?](#)

You can also [login with your owner-only consumer](#).

Close

Log in

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once logged in another box will pop up warning about the edits you will be about to undertake.

Upload edits to Wikidata

You are about to upload 2 edits to [Wikidata](#). Please check them carefully. Large edit batches should be submitted for [bot review](#) first.

occupation (P106) requires statement with property instance of (P31). Locate rows

i This property is expected to have another statement with property [instance of \(P31\)](#) such as on item [Peter Kenneth Buchanan \(Q21506603\)](#). If the item already has statements with property [instance of \(P31\)](#) in Wikidata, then this warning can be ignored. 2

You are logged in as: [Ambrosia10](#).

summary

maxlag Must be a positive integer. Leave this to the default value unless you know [how maxlag works](#).

Cancel

Upload edits

Screenshot of OpenRefine. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Add a summary of the edits you are about to make to Wikidata and then press the “Upload edits” button. Depending on the size of the dataset it may take some time for OpenRefine to add these statements to Wikidata.

Once the upload of edits for the reconciled values in the ORCID column have been completed, the above process should be repeated for the second column, that is the Wikidata Qid column.

Querying the Data

It is now possible to query Wikidata. For example this URL <https://w.wiki/FUq4> links to a simple query giving all the collectors who have Wikidata items with the statement “collection items at” the New Zealand Fungarium. Such queries can be generated either by the [Wikidata Query builder](#) or via the [Wikidata Query Service](#).

Alternatively Wikidata can be queried via several Wikidata API's See https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Data_access for further information.

Screenshot of the Wikidata Query Service. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

The results of queries generated via the Wikidata Query Builder or Query Service can be downloaded in multiple formats including as a csv file. These can be placed in OpenRefine. OpenRefine can then be used to extract data from Wikidata to enrich an institution's collection management system. Data such as the full name of the collector, their birth and death dates, and useful identifiers such as their Wikidata, ORCID or IPNI identifiers can all be obtained from Wikidata and, if an institution's collection management system allows, is able to be added in bulk imported to that system.

Helpful resources

Mabry, M., Flemming, A., Phillips, M., Zeringue-Krosnick, S. E., Kovacs, J., & Leachman, S. (2024). *Introduction to Bionomia*. BCEENET—Biological Collections in Ecology & Evolution Network, QUBES Educational Resources. <https://doi.org/10.25334/AXVE-E198>

Bionomia workshops <https://bionomia.net/workshops>

Bionomia help documentation <https://bionomia.net/help>

Basic editing of Wikidata via OpenRefine tutorial

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Tools/OpenRefine/Editing/Tutorials/Basic_editing